

D3.8 Ensemble Scenarios for Global Challenges

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List of Acronyms

Abbreviation acronym	Description
AI	Artificial Intelligence
ARM	Advanced RISC Machine (processor architecture)
CEMDB	City Energy Model Database
CFD	Computational Fluid Dynamics
CI/CD	Continuous Integration / Continuous Deployment
CKAN	Comprehensive Knowledge Archive Network (data management platform)
CoV	Coefficient of Variation
CPU	Central Processing Unit
D3.2	HiDALGO2 Deliverable 3.2 (Exascale Algorithms and Solvers)
ECMWF	European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts
EnSight	EnSight (post-processing and visualisation format)
EULAG	Eulerian/semi-Lagrangian numerical atmospheric model
FMU	Functional Mock-up Unit
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
HDF5	Hierarchical Data Format version 5
HPC	High-Performance Computing
HPDA	High-Performance Data Analytics
KUB	Ktirio Urban Building
LHS	Latin Hypercube Sampling
MARS	Meteorological Archival and Retrieval System (ECMWF)
MPI	Message Passing Interface
mUQSA	Multipurpose Uncertainty Quantification and Sensitivity Analysis toolkit
NIFI	Apache NiFi (data flow automation tool)
NO ₂	Nitrogen Dioxide
PBL	Planetary Boundary Layer

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PCE	Polynomial Chaos Expansion
PMV/PPD	Predicted Mean Vote / Predicted Percentage of Dissatisfied (thermal-comfort indices)
QCG	QCG-PilotJob (PSNC ensemble orchestration middleware)
RANS	Reynolds-Averaged Navier–Stokes (equations)
SLURM	Simple Linux Utility for Resource Management (workload manager)
SVD	Singular Value Decomposition
UQ	Uncertainty Quantification
VTI	VTK ImageData (file format)
waLBerla	widely applicable Lattice Boltzmann from Erlangen (HPC framework)
WP	Work Package
WPS	WRF Preprocessing System
WRF	Weather Research and Forecasting model

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Executive Summary

The deliverable, D3.8, presents the final consolidated report on ensemble scenario developments within the HiDALGO2 project. Building on the foundations established in D3.7, the document covers the methodological framework, enabling technologies, and pilot-specific implementations of ensemble-based simulation across five application domains. A shared ensemble lifecycle - define, generate, execute, analyse, use — is identified across the contributing pilots, while the specific methods and tools at each stage reflect the diversity of the underlying physical systems and decision-making contexts. For each pilot, specific ensemble implementations have been developed and demonstrated:

- Urban Air Project (SZE):** A full-factorial parametric ensemble of 48 steady-state NO₂ dispersion simulations has been executed over a 10.6 million cell mesh of the Győr city geometry, varying 16 wind directions and 3 wind speeds. Singular Value Decomposition of the resulting concentration fields identifies the dominant spatial dispersion patterns and the effective degrees of freedom, providing a basis for reduced-order modelling and scenario-based urban air-quality assessment.
- Urban Building (UNISTRA):** A reproducible ensemble framework has been integrated into the KUB simulation engine, supporting Monte Carlo and Latin Hypercube sampling with variance reduction, MPI-based parallel execution, and online statistical reduction using the Welford/Chan algorithm. The framework provides city planners with robust building rankings, exceedance probabilities, and quantile-based uncertainty indicators for energy demand and thermal comfort assessment.
- Renewable Energy Sources (PSNC):** Sensitivity analyses with up to 625 ensemble members have been conducted on up to 70,000 CPUs using the mUQSA toolkit and QCG-PilotJob orchestrator. Through Polynomial Chaos Expansion and Sobol indices, the analysis demonstrates that wind direction is the dominant uncertainty driver for local wind-speed predictions, while temperature and pressure perturbations have negligible influence.
- Wildfires (MTG):** The 50-member ECMWF MARS meteorological ensemble has been integrated with multiple ignition-point scenarios and planetary boundary layer parameterization experiments, producing the first comprehensive probabilistic assessment of wildfire behaviour under combined meteorological, ignition, and model-physics uncertainties.
- Material Transport in Water (FAU):** A systematic parameter-sweep approach has been implemented using the waLBerla framework, comprising 96 Couette flow simulations for model validation and over 100 thermally stratified

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simulations for AI surrogate data generation, executed across CPU and GPU architectures on EuroHPC systems.

Taken together, the work across the five pilots demonstrates that ensemble-based uncertainty quantification is computationally feasible at HPC scale, and that the resulting outputs provide a solid foundation for the downstream AI, HPDA, and uncertainty quantification activities in Work Package 4.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose of the document

This deliverable, D3.8, “Ensemble Scenarios for Global Challenges,” represents the final consolidated report on ensemble-scenario-related developments within the HiDALGO2 project. It is prepared in the context of Work Package 3 and is aligned with the description provided in the Grant Agreement, where D3.8 is defined as a report on identified ensemble scenarios, the result of independent simulation runs, and the application of AI for deriving additional insights. The work is structured around three complementary perspectives that are central to HiDALGO2 ensemble research: uncertainty quantification, input-space exploration, and sensitivity analysis. The purpose of this document is to present, the methodological foundations, enabling technologies, and pilot-specific applications of ensemble scenarios developed in HiDALGO2. In particular, the deliverable documents how ensemble approaches have been designed and applied across the project pilots to support the systematic exploration of simulation variability, the assessment of model sensitivity to uncertain inputs and parameters, and the extraction of additional knowledge through AI-supported analysis. It also positions the ensemble work in relation to other project activities, especially those concerning AI for Global Challenges and Uncertainty Quantification, and thereby provides a clear account of the relevance, maturity, and added value of ensemble-based approaches within the overall HiDALGO2 framework.

1.2 Relation to other project work

The work presented in this deliverable is closely connected to other activities in HiDALGO2, to the project’s developments in Artificial Intelligence and Uncertainty Quantification. The ensemble scenarios and the associated technologies described in D3.7 are used in Task T4.3 (Artificial Intelligence for Global Challenges) and Task T4.6 (Uncertainty Quantification), where they provide the basis for structured multi-run simulation campaigns, systematic scenario exploration, and the generation of data and insights for downstream analysis. In this sense, D3.7 forms an important bridge between the ensemble-oriented developments in WP3 and the data exploration, AI, and uncertainty-related activities in WP4. The results obtained from simulations using the ensemble scenarios are reflected in the related HiDALGO2 deliverable streams, most notably D4.3, D4.4, and D4.5 (“Advances in HPDA and AI for Global Challenges”), as well as D4.9 and D4.10 (“Uncertainty Quantification”). This interconnection is consistent with the overall project structure, where D3.7 and D3.8 establish the ensemble-scenarios line within WP3, while the corresponding WP4 deliverables build on these methods and results from the perspective of AI, HPDA, and uncertainty-aware analysis. The relationship is therefore not only thematic but also methodological, since the ensemble workflows, tools, and simulation outputs described

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here support subsequent analytics, AI-based interpretation, and uncertainty quantification studies across the HiDALGO2 pilots.

1.3 Structure of the document

This deliverable is organised into six sections. [Section 1](#) (this section) introduces the deliverable, summarises its purpose, and outlines the relationship to related work within the HiDALGO2 project. [Section 2](#) establishes the methodological framework that underpins the ensemble scenarios across all pilots, covering the ensemble lifecycle, the sources of variation, the generation strategies employed, execution on HPC infrastructure, analysis approaches, and the downstream use for uncertainty quantification and decision support. [Section 3](#) describes the specific technologies and execution environments used by each pilot — Urban Air Project, Urban Building, Renewable Energy Sources, Wildfires, and Material Transport in Water — to generate and execute their ensemble scenarios. [Section 4](#) presents the detailed ensemble scenarios for each global challenge addressed in the project, including the pilot scope and objectives, the ensemble setup and varied inputs, the tools and frameworks employed, the results and findings, and the limitations and next steps for each pilot. [Section 5](#) provides the overall conclusions of the deliverable, and [Section 6](#) lists the consolidated references cited throughout the document.

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2 Methodological framework for Ensemble Scenarios

2.1 The Ensemble Lifecycle in HiDALGO2

In the context of HiDALGO2, an ensemble scenario is a coordinated set of simulation runs in which specific inputs, physical parameters, boundary conditions, or model configurations are systematically varied to study how the resulting outputs change. Rather than relying on a single deterministic simulation, the ensemble approach produces a range of outcomes that can be analysed statistically to characterise variability [1], identify dominant input drivers [2], and support more informed decisions. The ensemble workflow in HiDALGO2 follows a common lifecycle that can be summarised in five stages: define, generate, execute, analyse, and use. First, the relevant sources of variation are identified — these may include uncertain material properties, atmospheric forcing data, ignition or scenario configurations, or dimensionless physical parameters. Second, a set of ensemble members is generated, where each member represents a distinct simulation configuration. Third, the ensemble is executed on high-performance computing infrastructure, with the scale ranging from tens to hundreds of concurrent runs depending on the application. Fourth, the simulation outputs are analysed statistically to derive quantities such as means, variances, confidence intervals, sensitivity contributions, or probability estimates. Fifth, the results are used for a downstream purpose — whether that is informing urban planning, prioritising emergency response, improving forecast reliability, or generating training data for AI-based surrogate models. The specific methods and tools employed at each stage vary across the HiDALGO2 pilots, reflecting the diversity of the application domains. The following subsections describe each stage of this lifecycle, and [Sections 3 and 4](#) then present the detailed pilot-specific implementations and results.

2.2 Sources of Ensemble Diversity

The starting point for any ensemble scenario is the identification of what is to be varied across the simulation runs. In HiDALGO2, the sources of ensemble diversity differ substantially across the pilots, reflecting the nature of the underlying physical systems and the questions being addressed. These sources can be grouped into four broad categories.

The first category concerns physical and material parameters that govern the behaviour of the simulated system. In urban building energy simulation [3], these include envelope properties such as wall thickness and insulation thermal conductivity, which can be drawn from continuous probability distributions to represent real-world uncertainty in the building stock. In particle-laden flow simulation, the relevant parameters are dimensionless quantities such as the particle Reynolds

The second category involves atmospheric forcing and boundary conditions. In renewable energy simulation, the ensemble is constructed by perturbing key

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atmospheric variables — wind speed, wind direction, pressure, and temperature — in the output of a mesoscale weather model [5] before passing them to a high-resolution flow solver. In wildfire simulation, the ensemble draws on an operational meteorological forecast product comprising 50 members [6], each representing a slightly different realisation of the atmosphere through perturbations in initial conditions and model physics.

The third category covers discrete scenario and configuration choices. In the urban building pilot [7], a scenario catalogue maps building types to operational timetables, compliance standards, and weather forcing recipes, producing qualitatively different simulation setups. In the wildfire pilot, ignition-point location and planetary boundary layer parameterisation are varied as discrete configuration choices that are combined with the meteorological ensemble to expand the exploration space.

The fourth category is specific to ensemble campaigns designed for AI and surrogate model development. In the material transport pilot, a second ensemble configuration is deliberately constructed not to answer a physical question directly, but to generate large-scale, diverse training datasets for downstream AI-based surrogate models, covering a broad range of thermal and flow conditions.

These categories are not mutually exclusive. Several pilots combine continuous parameter variation with discrete scenario choices — for example, the wildfire pilot combines 50 meteorological ensemble members with 7 ignition scenarios and alternative model-physics settings within the same campaign. Similarly, the urban building pilot combines statistical sampling of uncertain material properties with a structured scenario catalogue. [Table 1](#) summarises the sources of variation across the pilots, along with representative examples. The detailed implementations are described in [Section 3](#), and the corresponding results and findings in [Section 4](#).

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Table 1 — Sources of ensemble variation across the HiDALGO2 pilots

Category	Pilot	What is varied	Representative examples
Atmospheric forcing / boundary conditions	Urban Air Project	Wind inflow direction and speed	16 wind directions (22.5° resolution) × 3 wind speeds (2, 5, 10 m/s) = 48 full-factorial configurations
Physical / material parameters	Urban Building	Building-envelope and material properties	Wall thickness (0.10–1.0 m), insulation conductivity (0.026, 0.033, 0.040 W/mK), drawn from uniform, beta, or categorical distributions
Physical / material parameters	Material Transport in Water	Dimensionless flow and thermal parameters	Particle Reynolds number (1–16), volume fraction (0.1–0.3), Prandtl number (1–2), Rayleigh number, particle-to-fluid conductivity ratio
Atmospheric forcing / boundary conditions	Renewable Energy Sources	Perturbed atmospheric variables in mesoscale model output	Wind speed (relative scaling ×1±0.5), wind direction (±52°), pressure (±17 hPa), temperature (±9 K) applied to WRF output files
Atmospheric forcing / boundary conditions	Wildfires	Operational meteorological forecast ensemble	50-member ECMWF MARS dataset with perturbations in initial atmospheric conditions and model physics
Scenario / configuration choices	Urban Building	Discrete operational and policy scenarios	Scenario catalogue mapping building types to operational timetables, compliance bundles, and weather forcing recipes
Scenario / configuration choices	Wildfires	Ignition location and model-physics settings	7 ignition points (1 central + 6 within 500 m radius), planetary boundary layer parameterisation schemes

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2.3 Ensemble Generation Strategies

Once the sources of variation have been identified, the next step in the ensemble lifecycle is to determine how the individual ensemble members are generated — that is, how the varied inputs are translated into a concrete set of simulation configurations. The HiDALGO2 pilots employ four distinct generation strategies, each suited to different types of input variation, computational constraints, and analysis objectives.

The first strategy is statistical sampling from probability distributions, as used in the Urban Building pilot. In this approach, uncertain parameters are assigned probability distributions — uniform, normal, lognormal, beta, or categorical — and sample values are drawn using either Monte Carlo or Latin Hypercube Sampling [1]. Monte Carlo sampling generates independent uniform variates and applies the inverse transform to produce parameter values from the target distribution. Latin Hypercube Sampling improves upon this by stratifying the unit interval into equally sized bins and assigning one sample per bin through a seeded permutation, which achieves better coverage of the input space for a given number of samples. To support pairwise scenario comparisons, a Common Random Numbers technique is available, in which deterministic seeds are derived from the base seed, parameter index, sample index, and building identifier, ensuring that corresponding samples remain aligned across runs and reducing the variance of estimated differences. The sampling scope can be configured as global, where the same sampled value is applied to all buildings, per-building, where each building receives an independent draw, or quantile-synchronized, where the same quantile of a distribution is applied across all buildings in a given member.

The second strategy is perturbation of existing model outputs, as used in the Renewable Energy Sources pilot. Here, the ensemble is generated by applying controlled modifications to the output files of a mesoscale weather model before they are passed to a high-resolution flow solver. The mUQSA toolkit [5] manages this process by establishing a directory structure for each sample, generating deviation files, and applying perturbations at selected time-points while linking unperturbed data via symbolic links to avoid unnecessary duplication. The number and distribution of perturbations are determined by a Polynomial Chaos Expansion with a third-order polynomial, which optimises for the minimum number of samples needed to achieve statistically valid results. Two perturbation methods are employed: relative scaling for wind speed, where cell values are multiplied by a factor centred on unity, and absolute offsets for wind direction, pressure, and temperature, where values are added to the existing data with a mean of zero.

The third strategy is the reuse of an external operational ensemble, as employed by the Wildfires pilot. Rather than generating meteorological variability internally, this pilot uses the 50-member ECMWF MARS medium-range forecast dataset [6], in which each member represents a slightly different realisation of the atmosphere produced by the forecast centre through perturbations in initial conditions and model physics. The pilot

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then extends this external ensemble by combining each meteorological member with internally defined scenario variations — specifically, seven ignition-point locations and alternative planetary boundary layer parameterisation schemes [8] — resulting in a substantially larger combined ensemble.

The fourth strategy is a systematic parameter sweep, as used in the Material Transport in Water pilot. In this approach, each ensemble member corresponds to a unique combination of input parameters selected from predefined ranges [4], and the parameter space is covered deterministically rather than through probabilistic sampling. Two configurations are run separately: a laminar Couette flow setup comprising 96 simulations for model validation and physical analysis, and a thermally stratified configuration [9] comprising more than 100 simulations for the generation of AI surrogate training data.

These four strategies span a methodological continuum — from mathematically principled sampling with variance reduction, through physics-informed perturbation, to operational data reuse and deterministic sweeps. The choice of strategy in each pilot is driven by the nature of the uncertain input, the computational cost per simulation, the dimensionality of the parameter space, and whether the primary goal is statistical inference or broad parameter-space coverage. Table 2 provides a compact comparison of the generation strategies across the pilots.

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Table 2 — Ensemble generation strategies across the HiDALGO2 pilots

Strategy	Pilot	Method	Sample count	Key characteristic
Full-factorial parametric sweep	Urban Air Project	Cartesian product of 16 wind directions × 3 wind speeds	48	Deterministic coverage of wind-condition space; no probabilistic sampling
Statistical sampling	Urban Building	Monte Carlo / Latin Hypercube with inverse transform sampling and Common Random Numbers	16–64 (demonstrator)	Principled coverage with variance reduction; supports multiple distribution types and spatial scopes
Perturbation of model outputs	Renewable Energy Sources	mUQSA toolkit with Polynomial Chaos Expansion (3rd-order)	256–625	Minimum sample count optimised by PCE; perturbations applied to selected time-points only
External operational ensemble	Wildfires	50-member ECMWF MARS forecast × 7 ignition scenarios × PBL variants	50 × 7 + PBL variants	Combines externally produced meteorological ensemble with internally defined scenario variation
Systematic parameter sweep	Material Transport in Water	Grid-based deterministic coverage of parameter combinations	96 (Couette) + 100+ (surrogate)	Full deterministic coverage; no probabilistic sampling

2.4 Execution on HPC Infrastructure

All HiDALGO2 ensemble campaigns are executed on EuroHPC or national high-performance computing systems, but the orchestration approaches differ in how ensemble members are scheduled, parallelised, and managed. A key practical distinction is whether the ensemble is coordinated inside the simulation application or outside it through external job management.

The Urban Building pilot follows an internal orchestration model. Its ensemble executor splits the MPI world into simulation groups [7], each processing one ensemble member with a configurable number of ranks. Multiple members are executed concurrently within a single job allocation, and optional I/O ranks can be used.

The remaining three pilots follow an external orchestration model. The Renewable Energy Sources pilot uses QCG-PilotJob [10][11], a middleware layer that manages the submission and scheduling of ensemble runs. Each sample is assigned to a single compute node, and the middleware handles parallel execution when resources are available or sequential execution when they are not, without affecting the final analysis. The Wildfires and Material Transport in Water pilots both use automated Slurm scripting workflows, where a master script generates one working directory and batch job per ensemble member. The Wildfires pilot runs its coupled fire–atmosphere simulations using a hybrid OpenMP and MPI configuration across multiple nodes per member, while the Material Transport pilot executes CPU-based runs in parallel multi-batch mode and GPU-based surrogate runs sequentially.

The computational scale varies considerably — from 16 to 64 concurrent samples in the Urban Building demonstrator, through 256 to 625 ensembles using up to 70,000 CPUs in the Renewable Energy pilot, to 96 simulations each utilising 1,024 CPU cores in the Material Transport pilot. [Table 3](#) summarises the execution setup across the pilots.

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Table 3 — HPC execution and orchestration across the HiDALGO2 pilots

Pilot	Orchestration	Parallelism	Scale
Urban Air Project	Automated case-generation scripts	Up to 2,048 cores per configuration	48 configurations; aggregate ~98,304 cores
Urban Building	MPI-based internal scheduler	Multiple members concurrent within one job; optional I/O ranks	16–64 samples × 40–701 buildings
Renewable Energy Sources	QCG-PilotJob middleware	Each sample = 1 node; fully independent	256–625 ensembles, up to 70k CPUs (Eagle)
Wildfires	Slurm batch scripts	Hybrid OpenMP+MPI; 2–6 nodes per member	50 members × 7 ignitions (Deucalion + Discoverer)
Material Transport in Water	Slurm batch scripts	Multi-batch parallel (CPU) or sequential (GPU)	96 runs × 1,024 cores; GPU runs on 8×A100

2.5 Analysis of Ensemble Outputs

The analysis methods applied to ensemble outputs in HiDALGO2 are closely linked to the generation strategy employed. Each approach to creating ensemble members naturally leads to a corresponding form of statistical or physical interpretation.

When ensemble members are generated through statistical sampling, as in the Urban Building pilot, the outputs lend themselves to moment-based and distributional statistics. The Urban Building framework computes mean, variance, standard deviation, coefficient of variation, and confidence intervals incrementally during execution using the Welford/Chan algorithm [1], avoiding the need to store or centralise all sample outputs. Threshold exceedance counters provide empirical probabilities that a given output — such as heating demand or a comfort indicator — exceeds a critical value, while bounded-memory quantile sketches produce approximate distributional summaries at the 5th, 50th, and 95th percentiles. This online reduction approach is essential for scaling ensemble analysis to large building stocks and long-time horizons on HPC systems.

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When the ensemble is constructed through perturbation of model inputs, as in the Renewable Energy Sources pilot, the natural analysis is sensitivity decomposition. The mUQSA toolkit computes absolute contributions of each perturbed input variable to the output standard deviation, producing spatial sensitivity maps. Sobol indices [2] are used to assess interaction effects between inputs. Additionally, HPDA post-processing is used to compute weighted averages of key variables across the domain, where weighting accounts for differences in accuracy between parameterisation schemes.

When the ensemble originates from an operational forecast product combined with scenario variation, as in the Wildfires pilot, the analysis focuses on spatial probability mapping [12]. The key outputs include the probability that a given point in the territory will be affected by fire, along with the mean, variance, coefficient of variation, and confidence intervals of fire impact variables. A particularly important finding is that ensemble agreement tends to decrease over simulation time, meaning that uncertainty in fire behaviour grows as the simulation progresses.

When the ensemble follows a systematic parameter sweep, as in the Material Transport in Water pilot, the analysis takes the form of parameter-response characterisation. The primary outputs are heat flux budget decompositions [13] showing the relative contributions of convective and conductive components across different combinations of Reynolds number, Prandtl number, and volume fraction. Convergence behaviour is also assessed, as not all parameter combinations may reach convergence within the allocated execution time.

When the ensemble follows a full-factorial parametric sweep over wind conditions, as in the Urban Air Project pilot, the analysis takes the form of dimensional reduction. The NO₂ concentration fields from all 48 ensemble members are assembled into a data matrix and analysed using Singular Value Decomposition to identify the dominant spatial dispersion patterns. The rate of decay of the singular values indicates the effective number of independent modes needed to represent the ensemble, which directly informs the feasibility of reduced-order modelling for scenarios not explicitly simulated.

The correspondence between generation strategy and analysis approach is not coincidental — the way an ensemble is constructed determines what can meaningfully be inferred from its outputs. [Sections 4.1 through 4.5](#) present the detailed results and findings for each pilot.

2.6 Downstream Use: Uncertainty Quantification and Decision Support

The ensemble campaigns in HiDALGO2 serve two complementary downstream purposes: quantifying uncertainty in simulation predictions and supporting informed decision-making by domain practitioners.

Uncertainty quantification is a central motivation across all five pilots. Rather than producing a single deterministic prediction, ensemble runs allow each pilot to

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characterise the range and confidence of simulation outputs [14] — whether that takes the form of confidence intervals and exceedance probabilities for building energy indicators, standard deviation maps for wind-flow predictions, temporal divergence patterns in fire-spread forecasts, or convergence behaviour across flow regimes in particle-laden systems. In each case, the ensemble transforms a point prediction into a distributional statement about what is known and what remains uncertain.

These uncertainty-aware outputs in turn support decisions made by domain practitioners. The Urban Building pilot provides city planners and energy analysts [15] with robust building rankings for retrofit prioritisation, threshold-based risk screening, and scenario-envelope comparisons expressed through quantile indicators [16]. The Renewable Energy Sources pilot enables infrastructure owners to identify high-sensitivity zones where forecast accuracy is most critical for energy production. The Wildfires pilot provides emergency response planners with a probabilistic view of potentially affected territory and evidence of when fire behaviour becomes uncertain over time. The Material Transport in Water pilot uses its ensemble results to validate numerical models across parameter ranges and to identify regimes where simulations fail to converge, informing both model development and subsequent computational workflows. The Urban Air Project pilot uses its ensemble results to characterise the dominant pollutant dispersion modes under varying wind conditions, supporting scenario-based urban air-quality assessment and future reduced-order modelling.

This connection between ensemble-based uncertainty quantification and domain-specific decision support is what links the work described in this deliverable to the broader AI, HPDA, and uncertainty quantification activities in WP4, as discussed in [Section 1.2](#).

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3 Technologies and Execution Environment for Ensemble Runs

3.1 Urban Air Project

The Urban Air Project pilot uses a high-resolution computational fluid dynamics solver to perform steady-state NO₂ dispersion simulations over the urban geometry of Győr, Hungary. The computational domain consists of a 10.6 million cell mesh that resolves the city's building geometry and street network. Each ensemble member corresponds to one converged steady-state simulation with a prescribed wind direction and wind speed as inflow boundary conditions, while the geometry, mesh, emission configuration, and solver settings remain fixed across all members.

The ensemble is generated using a full-factorial parametric sweep. Sixteen wind directions, covering the full compass circle at 22.5° resolution, are combined with three wind speeds — 2, 5, and 10 m/s — producing a total of 48 simulation configurations. The Cartesian product of these inputs is generated automatically, and each case is prepared, executed, and stored in a structured form that maintains traceability between the output and the corresponding wind conditions. Each simulation produces an EnSight output file containing the three-dimensional NO₂ concentration field. For ensemble-level analysis, the individual concentration fields are assembled into a matrix, where each column represents one ensemble member. Singular Value Decomposition is then applied to this matrix to identify the dominant spatial patterns and to determine the effective dimensionality of the ensemble — that is, how many independent modes are needed to represent the variability across wind conditions.

The simulations scale efficiently up to 2,048 cores per configuration, as reported in Deliverable D3.2. For the full 48-member ensemble, this corresponds to an aggregate computational scale of approximately 98,304 cores, highlighting the need for automated case preparation and efficient post-processing workflows.

3.2 Urban Building

The Urban Building pilot uses the Ktirio Urban Building (KUB) [7] application as the execution environment for ensemble simulations. KUB is a city-scale building energy modelling [17] workflow built on Feel++, C++, MPI and Functional Mock-up Units (FMUs). It combines location datasets stored in the City Energy Model Database (CEMDB), building geometry and metadata, weather time series, scenario descriptions and FMU-based thermal building models. The same executable can run deterministic simulations and ensemble campaigns; the ensemble mode is activated by providing an ensemble plan through `cem.ensemble.plan`.

The ensemble method is based on a JSON plan that describes how ensemble members are generated and how they are executed. The plan can contain explicit samples or sampler-based definitions. The implemented samplers support Monte Carlo and Latin Hypercube strategies [1], with deterministic seeding for reproducibility and a QMC entry point currently falling back to LHS when the QMC backend is

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unavailable. The sampling scope can be global, per-building or per-building with synchronized quantiles. This makes it possible to explore both coherent district-wide assumptions and building-level heterogeneity. Parameters can be drawn from uniform, normal, lognormal, beta or categorical distributions by inverse transform sampling. The current parameter targets include opaque-layer properties, transparent constructions, zone parameters, heating parameters, general model parameters and direct FMU variables.

The execution workflow is parallelized with MPI. For each ensemble member, KUB creates a simulation group with a configurable number of MPI ranks. Several members can therefore be processed concurrently, depending on the available world size and the requested group size. Optional I/O aggregation can reserve I/O ranks for collecting time-series data and writing aggregated HDF5 outputs. This separation is important for ensemble runs because the volume of per-building time-series data can otherwise become the main bottleneck.

Scenario management is handled through a scenario catalogue and scenario-lock workflow. Scenario sets are authored in YAML and map reusable catalogue bundles to building types, time horizons, forcing policies and execution profiles. They can be resolved by the Python `kub-dataset scenarios` command into executable lock files. The lock contains resolved catalogue references, hashes, provenance and a runtime section. The first executable runtime backend is `legacy_csv_v1`, which maps building types to scenario timetable CSV files. At C++ runtime, KUB validates the lock hash and timetable hashes, rejects unsupported schema versions, prevents path traversal, and adapts the resolved lock into the existing scenario timetable mechanism. When both a legacy scenario file and a scenario lock are configured, the lock is selected and a warning is emitted.

The main outputs of an ensemble run are isolated member directories, run-level statistics and a run manifest. Member outputs are written under `simulations/ensemble/<run_id>/sample_<id>/database/`, while aggregated ensemble outputs are written under `simulations/ensemble/<run_id>/ensemble/`. The statistics layer is designed as an iterative reduction layer rather than as a post-processing step that collects all sample outputs. Each rank or simulation group updates compact reducer states as values become available, and these states can then be merged hierarchically. This is essential for the HPC execution mode because storing or moving all per-building, per-time-step and per-sample values would create prohibitive I/O, memory and metadata costs.

The exact reducers cover counts, sums, weighted means, min/max values, Welford/Chan mean and variance, class histograms and probability-of-exceedance counters [3]. The quantile branch extends this model with a bounded-memory mergeable quantile sketch, exposed in the reducer registry as `quantile_sketch` and used by the ensemble aggregator to produce distribution summaries such as `ensemble_p05`, `ensemble_p50` and `ensemble_p95`. Unlike exact moments, quantiles cannot be reduced by a fixed-size arithmetic state without retaining ordering

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information. The implemented sketch therefore uses an iterative, approximate and mergeable representation, which is appropriate for HPC runs where exact global sorting of all sample values would be too expensive.

The exported quantities include counts, means, variance, standard deviation, coefficient of variation, confidence intervals, optional probability-of-exceedance indicators and, when the quantile reducer is enabled, selected quantiles. These quantities are selected because they support decision-oriented interpretation [14]: robust building rankings, threshold-based risk rules, temporal uncertainty bands and p05/p50/p95 scenario envelopes. Where the Parquet backend is enabled, KUB also produces schema-defined KPI summary tables for downstream analysis and dashboard workflows.

This execution environment is designed to support the three D3.8 perspectives. It supports input-space exploration through controlled variation of envelope, material, operational and scenario inputs; uncertainty quantification through statistical sampling and confidence intervals; and sensitivity-oriented analysis through repeated simulations over well-defined parameter ranges and categorical alternatives. The produced datasets are also suitable for AI-supported post-processing, because each sample is traceable through its plan, scenario lock, manifest and output artifacts.

3.3 Renewable Energy Sources

The main tool used is the QCG-PilotJob [10], [11] which orchestrate running all of the ensembles. The ensembles are either created manually, i.e. simulations models with different parametrization schemes, or are created on the fly by the means of the mUQSA toolkit [5], in case sensitivity analysis or uncertainty quantification needs to be performed additionally. In the latter case, an implementation of the perturber is provided to the toolkit. The goal of the perturber is to provide a variance to some of the input parameters of the EULAG model, which is the key component in RES pilot. In the configuration of the ensemble runs, the parameter space and variance method is defined, so that the mUQSA toolkit can generate configuration of all the ensembles runs. It is then up to the QCG-PilotJob to orchestrate each ensemble run, and mUQSA to analyse the results for sensitivity analysis and uncertainty quantification. The entire execution, including ensemble parameter generation, simulation, and results analysis, is performed on HPC cluster. The advantage of QCG-PilotJob is that the ensembles do not need to be run in parallel, but rather, depending on the cluster availability, some can run in parallel, while others are waiting in the queue, without any negative impact on the final analysis.

The last step is to aggregate results from all the ensembles. For this, HPDA processing is used to average each of the key variable across all the computed domain. Weighting average is possible in case parametrization schemes which gives more accurate results for a given variable comparing to the other ensemble. In Section 4, all of these aspects are covered in more details.

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3.4 Wildfires

The Wildfires pilot has defined a pipeline to run ensemble simulations. The pipeline is centred around the use and needs of the libraries WPS and WRF-SFIRE, which entail the pre-processing of the data with WPS and the proper simulation with WRF-SFIRE.

There are two sources of variation that are being considered: the meteorological conditions and the ignition point of the fire. The ignition points add an additional layer of variation but do not constitute a separate ensemble, [6] which comprises 51 forecasts each of which has a small variation in terms of model physics and initial conditions. These variations provide a range of possible future weather states. These forecasts cover a period of 15 days which is longer than what is needed for most wildfire simulations which goes from a few hours to a day or two.

The structure of the ensemble simulation consists of:

1. A data directory which contains the ECMWF medium-range forecasts (one file per ensemble) and geographical data of the region of the fire.
2. A simulation directory that contains the WPS and WRF-SFIRE configuration template files along with a configuration file for the ensemble run in which the allocated resources and other system configurations are specified.
3. When the ensemble simulation is run a directory per ensemble is created resulting in a top directory for the whole run and an individual directory for each ensemble: {simulation_name}/ensemble_# . Inside each ensemble directory the configuration created from the templates for each ensemble will be stored along with all the files generated in each step of the whole simulation, including the final results and logs.

As mentioned above, to generate this structure and launch the simulation a script is used with the following goals:

1. It contains the allocation of resources (number of nodes, MPI+OpenMP distribution of tasks and memory) needed for each stage of the simulation to run properly as each stage requires a different configuration.
2. It creates the structure of directories.
3. Organizes the files and configures data dependencies copying the configuration files and adapt them from the templates for each individual ensemble.
4. Handles execution of WPS executables and the WRF-SFIRE executables.
5. Handles the storage of the results

This script is based on Slurm scripts and is organised in sections:

1. General configuration: data locations, environment variables and executables locations.
2. Ensemble creation: generate ensemble directories, copy and modify configuration templates for each ensemble.

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3. A section per executable with resource allocation (nodes, tasks, memory, etc.) and executable execution.
4. A section for handling results storage.

Regarding the storage of the final results for later analysis or reference. HiDALGO2 Data Management offers an infrastructure ready for this, as described in Deliverable D4.2. This infrastructure, through the use of NIFI pipelines, provides the necessary support for automating the handling of all the data involved in the ensemble pipeline from the storage of input data in CKAN or Hadoop and its retrieval to the storage of the results. The current ensemble pipeline only deals with the later but the addition of input data retrieval using this infrastructure is readily implementable.

This pipeline has not encountered many issues in any regard, the main issues to keep track of during the design of an ensemble run are related with the appropriate allocation and configuration of HPC resources especially in regards to file storage and generation. WPS and WRF-SFIRE generate a large amount of log files and adding these to the input data needed, it is important to ensure that the number of ensembles is enough to ensure proper ensemble variability and uncertainty analysis within the available file number and disk storage quotas.

3.5 Material Transport in Water

The ensemble runs developed in this work are based on a systematic parameter-sweep methodology designed to investigate both the robustness of numerical models and the generation of datasets for AI-based surrogate modelling. Two primary ensemble configurations were considered. The first focused on a laminar Couette flow [4] problem with moving particles and non-stratified fluid conditions, aimed at studying heat flux budgets and the behaviour of conductive and convective heat transfer mechanisms. Ensemble members were generated by systematically varying parameters such as particle Reynolds number, particle volume fraction, and Prandtl number [4]. The second configuration targeted surrogate model development through generation of large-scale datasets from a simplified thermally stratified [9] particle-laden system with fixed particles. In this setup, parameters including particle diameter, Rayleigh number, thermal boundary conditions, and conductivity ratios [9][13] were varied to produce diverse training datasets for AI workflows. The simulations were executed using the waLBerla framework, a massively parallel lattice Boltzmann-based HPC framework for large-scale multiphysics simulations. Efficient architecture-specific computational kernels were generated using lbmpy and pystencils, enabling optimized execution across heterogeneous HPC architectures. Automated bash and Slurm scripting workflows were employed for ensemble generation, job submission, execution management, and post-processing. Depending on resource availability, simulations were executed either in parallel multi-job mode or sequentially for large GPU-based surrogate runs.

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4 Ensemble Scenarios for Global Challenges

4.1 Urban Air Project

This section builds on the work reported in D3.7, where the general motivation, methodological basis, and pilot-level role of ensemble scenarios were introduced. The present section extends that foundation by reporting the concrete implementation of the ensemble approach in the Győr NO₂ dispersion pilot. It describes the scenario design, execution workflow, generated outputs, and the use of SVD-based analysis to identify dominant pollution-spread patterns and effective degrees of freedom.

4.1.1 Pilot scope, objectives and decision-making context

The objective of this pilot is to investigate steady-state NO₂ dispersion over the urban geometry of Győr under a representative range of wind conditions. The pilot addresses the fact that pollutant dispersion in a city is highly dependent on wind direction and wind speed. While full scale unsteady simulations provide a more accurate model, it is reasonable to investigate the effect of wind direction and velocity on the pollution dispersion.

The ensemble scenario is based on high-resolution CFD simulations performed on a 10.6 million cell mesh of the Győr city geometry. Each ensemble member corresponds to one steady NO₂ dispersion simulation with a prescribed wind direction and wind speed. The simulation outputs are exported in EnSight format and later processed as a matrix of NO₂ concentration fields.

The ensemble provides added value by systematically exploring how the NO₂ plume changes under different inflow conditions. This is important because the same emission setup can lead to different affected areas depending on the wind. The results are relevant for urban air-quality assessment, scenario-based evaluation, and future reduced-order modelling.

The main inputs are the Győr geometry, the computational mesh, the NO₂ emission representation, and the prescribed wind forcing. The main outputs are steady NO₂ concentration fields for each ensemble member. The key variables of interest are the spatial NO₂ values, the differences between scenario outputs, and the singular values obtained from SVD analysis.

The forcing space consists of 16 wind directions and 3 wind speeds: 2 m/s, 5 m/s, and 10 m/s. This gives a total of $16 \times 3 = 48$ simulation configurations.

4.1.2 Ensemble setup, varied inputs and methods

The pilot uses a deterministic parametric ensemble. The ensemble members are generated by varying wind direction and wind speed while keeping the geometry, mesh, pollutant variable, and simulation workflow fixed. The design is a full-factorial scenario grid, where every wind direction is combined with every wind speed.

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The wind directions cover the full compass circle using 16 directions, corresponding to a 22.5° directional resolution. The three wind speeds represent low, medium, and high wind-speed cases. This setup primarily supports input-space exploration and sensitivity-oriented analysis. It also contributes to uncertainty-quantification-related work in a scenario-based sense, although no probabilities are assigned to the individual wind cases.

After the simulations are completed, the NO₂ fields are read from the EnSight outputs and assembled into a matrix X, where each column represents one ensemble member. Singular value decomposition is then applied:

$$X = U\Sigma V^T$$

The singular values describe the importance of the dominant modes in the ensemble. A fast decay of the singular values indicates that only a small number of spatial patterns are needed to represent the ensemble, while a slower decay indicates a higher effective degree of freedom.

Table 4 — Varied ensemble inputs for the UAP wind speed and direction parameter sweep

Varied input	Values	Role
Wind direction	16 directions	Controls plume orientation and affected urban areas
Wind speed	2, 5, 10 m/s	Controls transport strength and dilution
Geometry and mesh	Győr, 10.6M cells	Fixed computational domain
Pollutant	NO ₂	Target scalar field
Simulation type	Steady-state	One converged field per scenario

4.1.3 Tools, Frameworks, workflow and execution environment

The workflow consists of simulation, ensemble execution, and post-processing. First, steady NO₂ dispersion simulations are performed on the 10.6 million cell Győr mesh. The only varied inputs are wind direction and wind speed. Each case produces an EnSight output containing the NO₂ concentration field.

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Second, the 48 configurations are generated from the Cartesian product of 16 wind directions and 3 wind speeds. The workflow prepares each case, executes the simulation, and stores the result in a structured form so that each output remains traceable to its wind direction and wind speed.

Third, the EnSight outputs are read and converted into a matrix representation. The SVD of this matrix is then used to determine the dominant modes and the effective dimensionality of the ensemble.

The simulations are measured to scale efficiently up to 2,048 cores per configuration, as reported in D3.2. For 48 configurations, this corresponds to an aggregate ensemble scale of 98,304 cores. This execution scale highlights the need for automation, consistent case preparation, and efficient post-processing.

4.1.4 Results and Findings

The ensemble campaign generated 48 steady NO₂ dispersion scenarios for the Győr city geometry. The scenarios cover 16 wind directions and 3 wind speeds, providing a structured dataset of pollutant-spread patterns under different meteorological conditions.

The main simulation output is the set of NO₂ concentration fields exported in EnSight format. These fields are assembled into the matrix X, with one NO₂ field per ensemble member. The main analysis result is the singular-value spectrum obtained from SVD. The dominant components of this matrix are visualised in [Figure 1](#).

Figure 1. Singular values of the NO₂ ensemble matrix on a semi-log scale.

The singular-value spectrum is strongly dominated by the first modes. The first singular value is 4.30×10^4 , almost three times larger than the second value, 1.50×10^4 . Based

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on squared singular-value energy, the first mode captures approximately 71.8% of the total ensemble energy, the first 5 modes capture 92.0%, the first 8 modes capture 95.7%, and the first 14 modes capture 99.3%.

This indicates that the 48 NO₂ dispersion fields have a relatively low effective dimensionality. Although all 48 wind-speed and wind-direction configurations were simulated, most of the dominant pollution-spread behaviour can be represented by a much smaller number of SVD modes. The first modes mainly describe the major plume-orientation and transport patterns, while later modes represent smaller local corrections.

The spectrum shows that the ensemble is suitable for reduced-order representation. Depending on the required accuracy, 5 modes would already capture more than 90% of the ensemble energy, 8 modes more than 95%, and 14 modes more than 99%.

4.1.5 Summary, limitations and next steps

This pilot demonstrates a structured ensemble scenario for steady-state NO₂ dispersion over the Győr city geometry. The ensemble consists of 48 simulations generated from 16 wind directions and 3 wind speeds, executed on a 10.6 million cell mesh and exported as EnSight NO₂ concentration fields. The outputs are assembled into a matrix and analysed using SVD to identify dominant dispersion modes and estimate the effective degrees of freedom of the pollution-spread response.

The current setup is a functional pilot implementation that supports systematic variability analysis and provides a basis for reduced-order or surrogate modelling. Its main limitations are that only wind direction and wind speed are varied, the simulations are steady-state, and no probability weights are assigned to the scenarios. Further work should interpret the singular-value spectrum, define the number of modes needed for a selected accuracy level, and extend the ensemble to additional physical inputs where relevant.

4.2 Urban Building

The Urban Building pilot extends the deterministic KUB [7] city energy simulation workflow reported in earlier HiDALGO2 work with an ensemble execution and scenario-management layer. The main contribution for D3.8 is the implementation of a reproducible ensemble framework for building energy simulations, together with a scenario catalogue and lock-file mechanism that makes scenario selection explicit and auditable. The work focuses on exploring how uncertain building parameters, material assumptions and operational scenarios influence energy demand, thermal comfort [3] and related urban-building indicators. The framework is implemented in the KUB codebase and is prepared for HPC execution through MPI-based sample scheduling.

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4.2.1 Pilot scope, objectives and decision-making context

The Urban Building pilot addresses district- and city-scale building energy simulation [17][18]. Its objective is to assess how the urban building stock responds to different physical, operational and scenario assumptions. The pilot is relevant for energy planning, retrofit prioritisation, comfort assessment and climate-resilience studies, where a single deterministic run is not sufficient to describe the uncertainty of the result [3].

The decision-making context is urban energy and building-stock analysis. City planners, energy analysts and infrastructure operators [15] need to compare expected energy demand and comfort indicators under multiple assumptions, rather than relying on a single value computed from one material database, one weather trace or one operational schedule. Ensemble simulations [16] provide a structured way to quantify variability, identify sensitive assumptions and produce robust indicators for downstream decision support.

The interpretation target is therefore not only the mean value of a KPI. The pilot is designed to support questions such as whether a building ranking remains stable under uncertainty, whether a comfort or load threshold is exceeded with high probability, whether a scenario envelope changes the sizing conclusion, and when during the simulated horizon uncertainty becomes operationally relevant. This is why the default outputs emphasize mean, variance, coefficient of variation, confidence intervals, exceedance probabilities, temporal uncertainty bands and quantile summaries.

The main inputs are location-specific CEMDB datasets. These include GIS metadata, LoD-0 and LoD-1 meshes, building typologies, FMU simulator datasets, weather time series, scenario timetable data and optional scenario-lock files generated from the scenario catalogue. The key outputs include heating and cooling heat flows, final and useful energy indicators, indoor and outdoor temperatures [19], comfort indicators such as PMV and PPD [20], solar shading coefficients, optional IAQ indicators, per-building reports, global KPI summaries and time-series datasets.

The ensemble approach adds value over a single simulation because it makes the variability of these outputs explicit. Instead of answering only what the model predicts for one assumed configuration, KUB can answer how the result changes when envelope parameters, material conductivity, operational schedules or scenario mappings are varied over a controlled exploration space. This is essential for sensitivity analysis [2] and for the creation of AI-ready datasets where each sample is linked to its generating assumptions.

4.2.2 Ensemble setup, varied inputs and methods

The ensemble setup is driven by an ensemble plan JSON file. A plan may list explicit samples, or it may define a sampler, a set of parameters, an application filter and

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optional I/O and workflow settings. Sampler-based plans generate reproducible samples from the building set discovered during model initialization. The current implementation supports global sampling, per-building sampling and per-building quantile-synchronized sampling. Global sampling applies the same sampled value to all selected buildings, while per-building sampling allows each building to receive independent parameter values. Quantile-synchronized sampling is used when the same quantile of a distribution should be applied across buildings in one member.

The mathematical form of the sampling process is the following. Let θ denote the uncertain input vector and let $Y = Q(u(\theta))$ be a quantity of interest derived from the building simulation, for example annual heating demand, a comfort metric, or a time-series value at a given building. For each parameter θ_i with cumulative distribution function F_i , KUB samples a probability value $u_i \in [0, 1]$ and applies the inverse transform $\theta_i = F_i^{-1}(u_i)$. In Monte Carlo mode the u_i values are independent uniform variates. In Latin Hypercube mode the interval $[0, 1]$ is stratified into M bins for each parameter dimension and a seeded permutation selects one bin per sample, improving coverage of the input space for a fixed sample count. The Common Random Numbers option derives deterministic seeds from the base seed, parameter index, sample index and building identifier, so corresponding samples remain aligned across comparable runs. This reduces the variance of scenario differences because $\text{Var}(Y_1 - Y_2) = \text{Var}(Y_1) + \text{Var}(Y_2) - 2 \text{Cov}(Y_1, Y_2)$.

The Table below summarizes the main exploration dimensions implemented for the Urban Building pilot.

Table 5 — Main exploration dimensions implemented for the Urban Building pilot

Varied input or method	Implemented exploration space	Example in the repository	D3.8 perspective
Opaque envelope thickness	Uniform and beta distributions applied to wall or exterior wall layers	plan_global_thickness_lhs.json varies wall layer thickness from 0.10 m to 1.0 m; plan_quantile_sync_beta.json uses a beta distribution from 0.02 m to 0.25 m	Input-space exploration, sensitivity analysis, UQ

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Varied input or method	Implemented exploration space	Example in the repository	D3.8 perspective
Insulation thermal conductivity	Categorical or uniform variation of the lambda field	plan_per_building_material_m c.json samples values 0.026, 0.033 and 0.040 with probabilities 0.2, 0.5 and 0.3	UQ, material uncertainty
Sampling strategy	Monte Carlo and Latin Hypercube sampling with deterministic seeds	Plans use base_seed=1234, LHS or MC, and sample counts such as 16 or 64	Reproducibility, UQ
Variance reduction	Common Random Numbers through deterministic seed derivation	Repeated runs can compare corresponding samples instead of unrelated random draws	Sensitivity analysis, UQ
Spatial scope	Global, per-building and quantile-synchronized per-building scopes	Plans under data/locations/*/plans/ reuse the same ensemble definitions across several locations	Input-space exploration
Scenario mappings	Scenario sets map catalogue bundles to building types and resolve to executable locks	scenario_set.quickcheck.yaml maps residential building types to baseline French RE2012 bundles and a CI quick check bundle	Scenario exploration, reproducibility
Operational timetables	Executable legacy_csv_v1 backend maps building types to	Scenario locks reference timetable paths and SHA-256 hashes timetable CSV files	Scenario execution, provenance

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Varied input or method	Implemented exploration space	Example in the repository	D3.8 perspective
Output and threshold processing	Optional filters, time-series stride, confidence level and threshold rules	Ensemble statistics export includes mean, variance, standard deviation, confidence intervals and probability of exceedance	UQ, AI-ready data
Iterative UQ reductions	Mergeable states for Welford moments, min/max, threshold exceedance, histograms and quantile sketches	The statistics reducers and ensemble aggregator compute ensemble_mean, ensemble_std, ensemble_min, ensemble_max, ensemble_p05, ensemble_p50 and ensemble_p95 without collecting all raw samples	HPC execution, UQ, AI-ready summaries

The current scenario catalogue includes components and bundles for building parameters, compliance references, operations, weather and air-quality forcing recipes, IAQ, interventions, controls, events, KPIs and execution profiles. In the first executable backend, scenario-set resolution produces timetable-based runtime data that can be consumed by the C++ simulation engine. Richer fields such as time_window, forcing_policy, execution and component_links are preserved in the lock provenance and are available for future backends that will directly modify weather forcing, model parameters or FMU configuration.

4.2.3 Tools, Frameworks, workflow and execution environment

The Urban Building ensemble workflow uses the following main tools and frameworks [7] as in below table.

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Table 6 — Urban Building ensemble workflow: main tools and frameworks

Layer	Tools and components	Role in the ensemble workflow
Simulation core	KUB C++ application, Feel++, MPI, FMU runtime	Executes the building energy model for each sample
Dataset layer	CEMDB layout, manifests, PathManager, DataRegistry	Resolves location inputs, shared simulator datasets and run outputs
Scenario layer	cemdb/scenarios, Python kub-dataset scenarios, scenario locks, C++ scenario loader	Resolves catalogue scenario sets into executable, hash-checked runtime inputs
Sampling layer	C++ EnsemblePlan, ParameterSample, deterministic random seeds	Generates parameter maps for each ensemble member
Execution layer	EnsembleExecutor, EnsembleWorkflow, MPI communicators, optional I/O ranks	Schedules samples over MPI groups and collects results
Analytics layer	iterative reducers, Welford/Chan moments, min/max and exceedance reducers, quantile sketch branch, HDF5 time-series aggregation, JSON and optional Parquet/GeoParquet sinks	Produces ensemble summaries and downstream analysis artifacts without requiring all raw samples to be gathered on one process

The ensemble can be viewed as a structured campaign rather than a collection of unrelated runs. A campaign defines samples $m = 1, \dots, M$, dispatches building or scenario tasks (m, b) , computes observables $Y_{\beta}^m(t_k)$, and reduces them online into statistics such as $\mu_{\beta}(t_k)$, $\sigma_{\beta}(t_k)$, probability of exceedance and selected quantiles. This separation between sample identity and reduction state is what enables online statistical reduction on HPC.

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The practical workflow is as follows:

1. A location dataset is prepared under CEMDB, including GIS metadata, mesh files, weather files, scenario data and a manifest.
2. A scenario set is optionally resolved into a lock file using the Python scenario service. The lock freezes catalogue references, source hashes and executable timetable mappings.
3. An ensemble plan JSON is selected or generated. The plan defines the sampling strategy, varied parameters, sample count, group size and optional I/O settings.
4. KUB is launched with MPI using the standard CEM executable and the ensemble plan option. A scenario lock can be supplied through `cem.scenarios.lock.filename`.
5. During initialization, KUB builds the city energy model, gathers the global building descriptors, prepares deterministic samples and broadcasts the sample descriptions to the ranks.
6. The executor splits the MPI world into simulation groups. Each group applies the parameter map of its assigned sample, runs the simulation and writes member outputs.
7. Scalar and time-series outputs update iterative reducer states [3]. Only the selected member outputs, compact reducer states and final summaries need to be written. If enabled, I/O ranks aggregate time-series data and write HDF5 outputs.
8. The run-level manifest and statistics files are written under the ensemble run directory for later validation, dashboard use and AI/UQ post-processing.

The parallel execution model follows the communicator structure introduced in the Ensemble UQ presentation. If M is the number of samples, P the number of concurrent sample groups, N_{sim} the number of simulation ranks per sample and N_{io} the number of optional I/O ranks, the target rank layout is:

$$N_{total} = P N_{sim} + N_{io}$$

Each simulation group processes approximately $[M/P]$ samples sequentially. Under the usual assumption that simulation time dominates communication time, the ideal wall-time model is:

$$T_{wall} \approx \frac{M}{P} T_{sample} + T_{comm}$$

This model is useful for selecting the number of ensemble groups and the number of ranks per sample. It also explains why dedicated I/O ranks are useful for larger ensembles: they move the workflow from many independent per-rank writes toward batched aggregation of the selected quantities of interest.

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The same reasoning applies to UQ analytics. Let B be the number of buildings, T the number of stored time steps, K the number of quantities of interest and M the number of ensemble members. A raw post-processing strategy scales as:

$$raw_{data} \approx O(M B T K)$$

This is not the desired execution model for large locations or long campaigns. Moment reducers keep fixed-size state per quantity, threshold exceedance reducers keep one counter per threshold, and quantile sketches keep bounded state controlled by the sketch capacity. Exact quantiles would require retaining the full sample order or performing a distributed selection over all values; the branch supporting quantiles therefore uses a more complicated but scalable iterative sketch.

The execution can be summarized as:

The main command-line interface is:

```

    mpiexec -n <ranks> --bind-to core build/default/src/feelpp_kub_cem \
    --config-file <location.cfg> \
    --cem.ensemble.plan=<plan.json> \
    --cem.ensemble.export=<ensemble_statistics.json>
  
```

When scenario locks are used, the command also includes:

```

    --cem.scenarios.lock.filename=<location>/manifests/<scenario_set>.lock.json
  
```

The repository contains reusable ensemble plans for several locations, including the cities of Kernante, Tonnoy, Rochefourchat, Menil-Saint-Michel, Huez, Arz, Flavigny-sur-Moselle, Hipsheim and Saint-Malo. The common plan families are a global LHS exploration of envelope thickness, a per-building Monte Carlo exploration of insulation conductivity and a quantile-synchronized beta exploration of insulation thickness. Additional small test plans cover categorical parameters, explicit workflow hooks and minimal execution checks.

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4.2.4 Results and Findings

The main result for the Urban Building pilot is a completed and integrated ensemble execution framework in KUB. The framework covers sample generation, MPI scheduling, scenario-lock ingestion, per-sample output isolation, ensemble statistics and manifest-based artifact tracking. This represents the operational basis required to run the Urban Building ensemble campaigns for uncertainty quantification, input-space exploration and sensitivity studies.

The numerical evidence presented here is based on representative reports and demonstrator ensemble results from the project repository. A larger ensemble scenario campaign is planned as the next step, with corresponding run manifests, statistics, and figures to be archived upon completion. The repository contains representative reports for several locations, which demonstrate the output variables and reporting structure used by the ensemble aggregation layer.

Table 7 — Computing time report (Urban Building demonstrator)

Location report	Number buildings of in report	Time horizon represented in report	Time step
Kernante	40	86,400 s	3,600 s
Menil-Saint-Michel	16	864,000 s	3,600 s
Rochefourchat	4	864,000 s	3,600 s
Tonnoy	701	86,400 s	3,600 s

These reports include weather data, geolocation data, time steps and building-level outputs such as PMV, PPD [20], heating and cooling heat flows, exterior heat flow and temperature indicators. They are used as evidence that the reporting chain exposes the quantities needed for the ensemble statistics. In ensemble mode, the same quantities are accumulated across samples and exported as mean, variance, standard deviation, coefficient of variation, confidence intervals and quantile summaries.

Currently the KUB Ensemble & UQ reports a representative district demonstrator snapshot that is useful for interpreting the current status of the pilot. The case contains 40 buildings in the urban dataset, 27 buildings effectively simulated after filtering and preprocessing, 16 uncertainty samples, 8 parallel processes and a one-week dynamic horizon with hourly resolution.

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The implemented ensemble plans provide concrete input spaces for initial campaigns. The global wall-thickness LHS plan defines 16 samples over a 0.10m to 1.0m thickness range. The per-building material Monte Carlo plan defines 64 samples over three insulation conductivity classes. The beta quantile-synchronized plan defines an asymmetric distribution for insulation thickness from 0.02m to 0.25m. These definitions are suitable for assessing how envelope uncertainty propagates to heating/cooling demand and comfort indicators.

Table 8 — Representative reports (Urban Building heating demand)

Building id	QFlowHeating mean	CoV	95% CI width
70433771	8,188.5	1.41%	122.7
70444137	2,178.6	2.22%	51.5
70444293	2,078.4	2.09%	46.3
3695210869054885	2,077.6	1.90%	42.1
70435253	1,132.5	2.60%	31.3

Table 9 — Comfort reports (Urban Building PMV/PPD)

Building id	PMV mean	PPD mean	95% PMV CI width
70444137	-0.969	0.249	0.00539
70433771	-1.043	0.280	0.00457
3695210869054885	-1.047	0.281	0.00520
70435253	-1.031	0.275	0.00645

The interpretation is that the largest heating-demand building remains clearly separated from the rest of the sample. In this case, the uncertainty band is small enough relative to the gap between the top building and the following group to support

a robust retrofit-prioritisation discussion [15][16]. This illustrates the intended decision use of the ensemble: act on stable ordering and uncertainty-aware risk indicators, not on one deterministic value. The comfort indicators from the same demonstrator show a different type of conclusion.

Here the PMV uncertainty band [20] is narrow compared with the absolute comfort level. The resulting conclusion is that, over this horizon and for this wall-thickness uncertainty driver, additional samples of the same parameter are unlikely to change the comfort interpretation. If the comfort result is unacceptable, the next useful study should vary another uncertain input or test an intervention scenario.

The scenario-lock workflow is another important result. It makes scenario execution reproducible by recording the scenario-set source, catalogue hash, resolved mappings, runtime timetable paths and SHA-256 hashes. This is an improvement over direct use of mutable scenario files because a run can be checked against the exact scenario payload that was resolved before execution. The C++ runtime verifies the lock and timetable hashes before adapting the scenario data into the simulation.

The UQ statistics are computed without storing all raw samples. For each scalar or per-building output, KUB keeps the state (n, mean, M2), where M2 is the accumulated centred sum of squares. When a new value x is observed, the accumulator updates the count, mean and M2 in one pass. Independent partial accumulators can be merged with the Chan/Welford pairwise formula [1], which makes the reduction suitable for MPI. The final sample variance is M2/(n-1) for n > 1. Confidence intervals for the mean use the Student-t form:

$$\text{mean} \pm T_{n-1, 1-\frac{\alpha}{2}} \text{stddev} / \sqrt{n}$$

The coefficient of variation is reported as stddev/mean, and threshold rules are evaluated as empirical probabilities of exceedance:

$$\text{POE}(\tau) \approx \frac{\text{count}(Y > \tau)}{n}$$

This is the mathematical basis for interpreting ensemble outputs as uncertainty summaries rather than as a collection of unrelated deterministic runs.

Quantiles require a different treatment. They are distributional summaries and are not directly mergeable through a fixed-size moment state. The quantile branch therefore implements QuantileSketchReducer, a bounded-memory sketch that receives values iteratively, compacts sorted levels when their capacity is exceeded, merges corresponding levels from independent partial sketches, and finalizes selected quantiles from weighted sketch items. The default ensemble aggregation uses the requested quantiles p5, p50 and p95, which are exported as ensemble_p05, ensemble_p50 and ensemble_p95 in the KPI summary table.

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This quantile computation is intentionally approximate. Its accuracy depends on the sketch capacity and on the reduction structure, while its memory footprint remains bounded with respect to the number of samples. This trade-off is the reason the method is appropriate for ensemble execution on HPC systems: exact quantiles remain possible for small diagnostic runs, but they do not provide the scalable execution path needed for the pilot campaigns.

The associated presentation material also reports a small scalability exercise for a Kernante ensemble case with global wall-thickness LHS sampling, a one-year hourly simulation and concurrent sample groups. The reported wall times decrease from 42.3 minutes on one rank to 23.1 minutes on four ranks and 12.7 minutes on eight ranks, corresponding to speedups of 1.83 and 3.33. These values should be treated as execution evidence for the framework and not as final pilot results, because the final campaign should be archived with its corresponding run manifests and statistics.

The technical findings from the implementation are the following:

1. The same KUB executable can support deterministic and ensemble runs, which reduces duplication and keeps the single-run validation path relevant for ensembles.
2. MPI group scheduling is appropriate for the pilot because each ensemble member can use several ranks while multiple members are processed concurrently.
3. Separating per-sample outputs from run-level ensemble outputs is necessary for traceability and for scalable post-processing.
4. Iterative reducer states are part of the execution model, not only a reporting convenience. They avoid the need to centralize all sample values and therefore make large ensemble UQ feasible on HPC systems.
5. The quantile-sketch branch adds distributional summaries to this reducer model. It gives the framework p05/p50/p95 indicators without a global sort, at the cost of an explicit approximation policy.
6. Scenario locks provide a practical bridge from a high-level scenario catalogue to the existing timetable-based C++ scenario runtime.
7. The current result artifacts are already suitable for downstream AI and UQ workflows because each run records sample identity, scenario provenance, statistical summaries and a manifest of produced files.
8. The most useful decision products are compact: ranked KPI tables with uncertainty, probability-of-exceedance rules for thresholds, dynamic uncertainty bands, p05/p50/p95 envelopes and maps of robust or uncertain hotspots.

The repository currently provides the implemented framework, example exploration definitions, and representative demonstrator evidence. The next integration step is to

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execute the selected larger ensemble campaigns on the target HPC environment and archive the resulting numerical tables and figures.

4.2.5 Summary, limitations and next steps

The Urban Building pilot now has a reproducible ensemble framework integrated with the KUB [7] simulation engine. The implementation supports deterministic sample generation, MPI execution, scenario-lock based runtime configuration, per-sample output isolation and ensemble-level statistics. This provides a mature technical basis for uncertainty quantification and input-space exploration of urban building simulations [3][14].

The main limitations are related to the maturity of scenario execution and the absence of a final archived production ensemble campaign in the repository. The first executable scenario backend is intentionally conservative: it maps scenario sets to the existing legacy timetable mechanism. It preserves richer catalogue fields such as time windows, forcing policies and component links as provenance, but it does not yet apply all of these fields directly to weather forcing, model parameters or FMU configuration. The QMC sampler entry point currently falls back to LHS, and the spatial-field sampling mode remains a placeholder. Building-level reporting and time-series storage can also become expensive for large locations, so production campaigns need explicit output filtering and I/O planning.

The quantile sketch support also needs to be treated explicitly in the final campaign protocol. Unlike mean, variance, min/max and threshold counts, the quantile reducer is an approximate bounded-memory method. The final D3.8 numerical campaign should therefore document the selected sketch capacity, the reduction policy and the validation checks used for tail-sensitive indicators. Exact quantile computation should be reserved for small validation cases or offline checks, not for the primary HPC execution path.

The immediate next step is to execute the selected larger ensemble scenarios on the target HPC system, archive the run manifests and statistics, and add the resulting figures or summary tables. On the software side, the next development priorities are to extend the executable scenario backends beyond timetable CSV files, add direct weather and parameter overlays from scenario catalogue components, complete QMC/spatial-field sampling, and connect the ensemble outputs more directly to the AI and UQ analysis workflows in WP4. A further sensitivity-analysis extension is to add dedicated Sobol/Saltelli-style sampling [2] so that first-order and total-effect indices can be estimated directly from KUB ensemble campaigns. On the decision-support side, the priority is to turn the existing summaries into routine templates for retrofit ranking, threshold-based risk screening, scenario-envelope comparison and dashboard drill-down [17][18] from city-level patterns to building-level behaviour.

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4.3 Renewable Energy Sources

In Deliverable D3.7, ensemble scenario for RES-damages was described in details, including tools and methodology. The second ensemble scenario for RES refers to standard ensemble usage, where the goal is to take into account all available data and limit the uncertainties. Speaking of the latter, these are related to the information used by simulation models treated as input data and boundary conditions, but more important to the model itself and the available parametrization or physics schemes.

4.3.1 Pilot scope, objectives and decision-making context

The main objective of the RES pilot is supporting development and operation of renewable energy sources infrastructure. It may concern forecasting of electricity produced by the photovoltaics and wind farms, assessing probability of damages to the infrastructure, support finding best spots for the infrastructure, etc. As mentioned in [Section 3](#), the main tools used are QCG-PilotJob [15][16] to orchestrate ensemble runs, and the mUQSA toolkit [17] to support ensembles generation, uncertainty quantifications, and sensitivity analysis studies. The ensemble scenarios are important for many different reasons. To provide an accurate forecast of energy predictions, different input data need to be considered, different parametrization schemes (because some variables may be modelled more accurate with one configuration of physics than the other), and even provide some perturbation to the data to minimize the uncertainties of the model. Ensembles are perfect solution for what-if scenarios – whenever finding a location for new infrastructure or pondering on possible damages, lots of simulations with different conditions need to be run in order to provide decision makers with a valuable insight. Speaking of decision-making, it is infrastructure owners and developers who benefit from ensemble runs.

In this Deliverable, the focus is given on using the ensembles for sensitivity analysis, but the approach described is applicable to the all aforementioned scenarios. The ensembles concern the main parts of the RES pilot – WRF coupled with the EULAG model. The inputs are the geometry/orographic data which is static and does not change (unless what-if scenarios are concerned). Other input concern initial weather data which may come from different global/mesoscale/regional models, here WRF is used. The ensembles are generated from WRF results, which are then used by EULAG. The output of the ensembles are a bunch of weather parameters, the most important ones for the pilots are these related to wind flows, solar irradiance, precipitation.

4.3.2 Ensemble setup, varied inputs and methods

In this scenario focus is given to sensitivity-oriented studies, which may be further extended to the uncertainty quantification. The mUQSA [5] workflow systematically manages perturbed model evaluations by first establishing a directory structure for each sample. A Sampler and Encoder collaborate to generate input sets and deviation

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files, which the Perturber then uses to modify specific files and time-points. These perturbations are applied across the domain via value offsets, scaling coefficients, or custom hard-coded methods. To maintain computational efficiency, the system saves only the altered files to the working directory while utilizing symbolic links for unperturbed data to prevent unnecessary copying.

The Ensemble setup leverages the Polynomial Chaos Expansion (PCE) sampling method [5] with a third-order polynomial, optimizing for the minimum number of samples required to achieve statistically valid results. The analysis incorporates varied inputs by perturbing four key atmospheric variables—wind speed, wind direction, pressure, and temperature—using values chosen to reflect typical climatic ranges or to maintain numerical stability.

Methodologically, the ensemble employs two distinct perturbation methods:

1. Relative Scaling: Used for wind speed, where cell values are multiplied by a factor (mean = 1).
2. Absolute Offsets: Used for direction, pressure, and temperature, where values are added to the existing data (mean = 0).

Notably, wind perturbations required a conversion from Cartesian components to polar coordinates to isolate speed and direction before being re-encoded for the simulation.

4.3.3 Tools, Frameworks, workflow and execution environment

Here is the general ensemble workflow:

1. The WRF model generates output (weather forecast) for a specific domain (area and time).
2. WRF output is perturbed. This stage creates many different WRF outputs - samples. A single output (sample) consists of many time-points. Not all the time-points are perturbed; only the chosen ones. The rest remains untouched.
3. The EULAG model performs a separate simulation for each sample.
4. Statistics from many samples, for a specific time-point and height are calculated. The analysis is orchestrated by the mUQSA (Multipurpose Uncertainty Quantification and Sensitivity Analysis) toolbox [5], which manages the end-to-end workflow from scenario definition to statistical output. The execution is partitioned into two distinct stages to optimize resource allocation:
 - I. Evaluation Stage: Conducted on the Eagle Supercomputer (PSNC) [10] using high-performance Proxima-CPU nodes (Intel Xeon Platinum 8480+). Since sample calculations are fully independent, the workflow scales linearly by assigning each sample to a single node, eliminating communication overhead between nodes.
 - II. Analysis Stage: Executed on smaller Altair nodes to conserve CPU hours, as this stage is single-core and non-scalable. This stage decodes specific time-points and vertical layers from the EULAG simulation results into a format mUQSA can process.

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The workflow, see [Figure 2](#), integrates the EULAG model with WRF output data. mUQSA's sampler generates perturbations applied directly to WRF files, which then serve as inputs for parallelized EULAG simulations orchestrated by QCG-PilotJob [10]. Upon completion, mUQSA performs sensitivity analysis study, and HPDA Python tool is used to average results from all ensembles. In this study, 256 and 625 ensembles were used, using up to 70k CPUs to run all the ensembles.

Figure 2. RES ensemble workflow (sensitivity analysis example)

4.3.4 Results and Findings

Four input variables—wind magnitude, wind direction, pressure (P), and temperature (T)—were perturbed to assess their impact on the system. Because WRF and EULAG represent wind through three separate Cartesian components, horizontal wind was converted to polar coordinates to perturb speed and direction independently before being converted back; vertical wind speed remained untouched. Uniformly distributed perturbations were applied such that the mean corresponded to a lack of perturbation, using standard deviations of $\sigma \approx 0.30$ for wind magnitude (relative factor of 1 ± 0.5), $\sigma \approx 30^\circ$ for direction ($0 \pm 52^\circ$), $\sigma \approx 10$ hPa for pressure (0 ± 17 hPa), and $\sigma \approx 5$ K for temperature (0 ± 9 K). One hour after application, the standard deviations of temperature (< 0.005 K) and pressure (< 5.3 Pa) remained marginal, falling significantly below weather forecasting precision limits. Similarly, the standard deviation of vertical wind (w) did not exceed 0.247 m/s and appeared only in negligible spots between tightly packed buildings. Because wind turbines are insensitive to vertical flow and these values were localized, these three variables were omitted from further analysis. Even if temperature and pressure deviations were two orders of magnitude higher, they would remain irrelevant to energy production sensitivity.

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The domain-wide mean wind speed was estimated at 3.4 m/s, dropping to 3.2 m/s in leeward areas. A maximum standard deviation of approximately 0.86 m/s was observed behind specific small-scale buildings, a significant value relative to the 3.4 m/s mean. This parameter is critical as it affects both wind turbine yield and the efficiency of PV systems, which are thermally sensitive to wind speed. While windward areas showed near-zero variance, leeward zones exhibited complex deviations as shown in [Figure 3](#) Standard deviation of the vertical wind speed (left) and standard deviation of the horizontal wind speed (right). 2, where vertical and horizontal wind speed maps are scaled to 0.43 m/s for contrast.

Figure 3 Standard deviation of the vertical wind speed (left) and standard deviation of the horizontal wind speed (right).

Sensitivity was evaluated using absolute contributions to standard deviation rather than Sobol indices to provide clearer spatial insights. Temperature and pressure perturbations contributed at most 0.16 m/s and 0.19 m/s respectively in very few irregular spots, confirming their insignificance. In contrast, wind speed and direction were the most influential. Wind speed perturbations contributed up to 0.26 m/s, creating regular but turbulent structures, while wind direction perturbations contributed up to 0.85 m/s, forming mostly laminar structures as seen in [Figure 4](#) Absolute contribution of horizontal wind speed perturbation to the wind speed deviation (left) and absolute contribution of wind direction perturbation to the wind speed deviation (right). 3. Total Sobol indices revealed no significant interactions, suggesting these primary factors act independently.

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Figure 4 Absolute contribution of horizontal wind speed perturbation to the wind speed deviation (left) and absolute contribution of wind direction perturbation to the wind speed deviation (right).

Analysis indicates that wind direction in built-up, leeward areas is the most sensitive variable to perturbations, though these effects are concentrated in specific terrain "streaks" rather than the entire domain. Because even temporary fluctuations in wind direction significantly impact long-term simulation results, high-fidelity input forecasts are essential for accurately predicting energy production in these regions. Finding the specific high-sensitivity streaks requires a custom analysis for each individual domain.

4.3.5 Summary, limitations and next steps

A series of analyses was performed to identify the most sensitive weather parameters. By running such analysis questions can be answered, such as does the input temperature deviation have any meaningful influence on the predicted local wind speeds above the buildings' top level, or does the change in the simulation write-interval lead to higher or lower sensitivity of any particular variable. This sensitivity analysis is intended to serve the purpose of identifying certain categories of areas that are particularly numerically susceptible to disturbances in input variables, as well as identifying the input variables themselves that will require particular attention, whose confidence will need to be increased as much as possible, to maximize the credibility of the model used in the second stage of energy generation forecasting - EULAG [10]. More detailed findings will be provided in Deliverable D4.10.

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4.4 Wildfires

The simulation ensemble designed in the Wildfires pilot is based on the deterministic workflow for fire spread and smoke dispersion simulations described in previous HiDALGO2 studies, to which it adds a layer for executing simulation ensembles and managing scenarios.

The main contribution to D3.8 is the implementation of a reproducible simulation suite framework for fire simulation and operational uncertainty assessment [8]. The work focuses on exploring how the uncertainty associated with atmospheric conditions and terrain topography influences fire behaviour in a pseudo-operational environment, from which the potential impact on areas surrounding the initial fire zone can be estimated.

4.4.1 Pilot scope, objectives and decision-making context

The Wildfires pilot project assesses the progression of fires in forest environments and also simulates the various pollutants emitted during combustion and their dispersion. Its objective is to identify potential areas affected by the fire or by the smoke it emits. The pilot project is relevant for analysing past situations and evaluating measures that could have been considered, as well as for operationally assessing potential affected areas in order to prioritize the defence actions to be taken—areas in which a single deterministic simulation is insufficient to account for the uncertainty of the outcome [12]. The context of decision-making and the prioritization of response actions requires evidence-based information that allows estimating which areas may be affected and the population and assets that may be impacted. The defined joint simulations offer a structured way to quantify the variability and probability of impact in a specific area and, based on this, generate robust indicators to support subsequent decision-making [12]. The purpose of the interpretation is not to identify the most likely simulation and the affected areas, but rather to provide a range of possibilities consistent with the current weather conditions and to demonstrate the extent to which we can rely on a deterministic fire path [8], or whether the envelope of the set of simulations covers a considerably larger area, affecting other assets; furthermore, to determine at what moment the fire’s behaviour begins to exhibit greater uncertainty, and how these results can become relevant in operational decision-making. Therefore, the analysis of the results yields various relevant statistics, such as the probability that a point in the territory will be affected by the fire, as well as the mean, variance, coefficient of variation, and confidence intervals for those variables considered most important in characterizing the potential impact of the fire.

4.4.2 Ensemble setup, varied inputs and methods

The pilot uses an ensemble based on European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) MARS data [6], with a spatial resolution of approximately 9 km. The ensemble members are generated by introducing small perturbations in the initial

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atmospheric conditions and model physics, allowing the representation of forecast uncertainty and variability [8].

Across the ensemble members, the main variations are introduced in the initial atmospheric conditions and, to a lesser extent, in model physics and boundary conditions. These perturbations generate slightly different realizations of the atmosphere, enabling the ensemble to capture forecast uncertainty and the range of possible meteorological evolutions [12]. Regarding the initial conditions, the simulations consider one ignition point together with six additional ignition points distributed within a radius of 500 m around the main location.

The exploration space considers the variability introduced by the 50-member ECMWF MARS ensemble meteorological dataset at approximately 9 km resolution, including variations in near-surface temperature (T2m), relative humidity, wind speed and direction. Different ignition scenarios are also explored using one central ignition point and six additional points distributed within a radius of 500 m. In addition, sensitivity analyses are performed by modifying the planetary boundary layer (PBL) parameterization in order to assess the relative contribution of meteorological uncertainty and model-physics uncertainty to wildfire spread predictions.

The proposed setup covers several D3.8 perspectives, mainly input-space exploration, uncertainty quantification (UQ), and sensitivity-oriented studies. The ensemble explores different meteorological scenarios through the 50-member ECMWF MARS dataset, including variations in temperature, relative humidity, wind speed and direction, and soil moisture, as well as different ignition locations. The framework is also designed to assess both meteorological uncertainty and model uncertainty by analysing the sensitivity of wildfire spread predictions to modifications in the planetary boundary layer (PBL) parameterization and other model-physics settings.

4.4.3 Tools, Frameworks, workflow and execution environment

As noted in [Section 3.4](#), the infrastructure designed for the operational generation of simulation ensembles provides the necessary support to automate the processing of all data involved in the ensemble process, from the collection of meteorological information obtained from the ECMWF or other meteorological services via NIFI, to its storage in CKAN or Hadoop and its subsequent transmission to the HPC server.

The workflow starts with the preparation of meteorological and static input data. Initial and boundary conditions are obtained from the 50-member ECMWF MARS ensemble dataset [6] at approximately 9 km resolution. Static geographical information defining the domain location and terrain characteristics is generated using Static Geography Data from University Corporation for Atmospheric Research. In addition, fuel-type and digital terrain model datasets are provided by Simmer Project with a spatial resolution of 25 m. Ensemble cases are generated by combining the 50 meteorological members with different ignition scenarios, including one central ignition point and six surrounding ignition points within a radius of 500 m, together with sensitivity experiments involving

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modifications of the planetary boundary layer (PBL) parameterization. Simulations are performed using the WRF-SFIRE coupled fire-atmosphere model [8] on an HPC environment using parallel execution with OpenMP and MPI. The simulations focus on wildfire events that occurred during the summer of 2025 in the northwestern region of Spain. Each simulation runs for 17 hours: the model initialization starts at 02:00 UTC, followed by a 12-hour atmospheric spin-up period, the wildfire ignition is introduced at 14:00 UTC, and the simulations finish at 19:00 UTC. Post-processing includes the extraction and analysis of wildfire spread outputs, ensemble statistics, and uncertainty metrics to evaluate the relative contribution of meteorological and model uncertainties. The ensemble simulations are executed on the Deucalion Supercomputer and Discoverer Supercomputer HPC systems using the SLURM workload manager for job scheduling and orchestration. Simulations are run in parallel using a hybrid OpenMP + MPI configuration. On Discoverer, executions use 2 nodes with 128 cores each, while on Deucalion simulations are performed on both x86 and ARM partitions using 6 nodes with 48 cores each. The workflow is highly automated through submission scripts that automatically generate an independent working directory for each ensemble member, prepare the corresponding input datasets and configurations, launch the simulations, and organize the resulting outputs for subsequent post-processing and uncertainty analysis.

The execution scale comprises 50 meteorological ensemble members from the ECMWF MARS dataset combined with 7 ignition scenarios, including one central ignition point and six additional ignition points distributed within a radius of 500 m. Additional variants are generated through sensitivity experiments involving modifications of the planetary boundary layer (PBL) parameterization and other model-physics setting. The study focuses on 4 wildfire events that occurred during the summer of 2025 in the northwestern region of Spain. This configuration results in a large ensemble of coupled fire-atmosphere experiments carried out on HPC infrastructures, generating extensive output datasets that include wildfire spread evolution, atmospheric fields, burned-area products, ensemble statistics, and uncertainty indicators related to both meteorological forcing and model configurations. The spatial distribution of these ignition scenarios is shown in [Figure 5](#).

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Figure 5. Spatial distribution of ignition scenarios used in the simulations, showing the central ignition point and six additional ignition points located within a 500 m radius around it.

4.4.4 Results and Findings

The ensemble study evaluates key uncertainty sources, including meteorological forcing, model physics, and ignition location [12]. It combines the 50-member ECMWF MARS ensemble with multiple ignition and model configurations, producing a comprehensive set of coupled fire-atmosphere simulations and outputs. The results show that the largest contribution to uncertainty in wildfire evolution is associated with atmospheric dynamics and local orography, which strongly influence fire spread patterns. Early-stage simulations indicate a high level of agreement among ensemble members, with similar fire perimeter evolution across most scenarios. However, as the simulation progresses, divergences between ensemble members become more pronounced, highlighting increasing uncertainty in fire propagation over time. Spatial analysis of burned-area maps reveals that while most ignition scenarios lead to consistent fire development in the initial hours, one ignition point shows very limited fire propagation in comparison with the other ignition locations considered. This behaviour requires further investigation, as it may be related to local fuel characteristics, fire-atmosphere interactions, or specific terrain and wind conditions at that location. The resulting burned-area distributions across the ensemble are shown in [Figure 6](#).

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Figure 6: Burned area obtained from WRF-SFIRE simulations for four different ignition points, showing the results of the 10 ensemble members for each ignition scenario.

4.4.5 Summary, limitations and next steps

The ensemble framework provides a first comprehensive assessment of wildfire behaviour under combined meteorological, ignition, and model-physics uncertainties [8]. It integrates the 50-member ECMWF MARS ensemble with multiple ignition configurations and sensitivity experiments, enabling a systematic exploration of coupled fire–atmosphere interactions and their associated variability.

The main objective is to provide a probabilistic view of the potentially affected area and to better assess the possible impact of wildfire behaviour across different points of the territory, supporting more informed risk evaluation and decision-making processes [12]. We do not observe major limitations in the analysis of the results, although we continue improving the workflows and methodologies. A key constraint in HPC environments is the large size of the output data and the high number of log files generated. Increasing the number of simulation points and running large WRF-SFIRE ensemble experiments significantly increases computational resource usage and produces a substantial amount of output data and logs. HPC systems often impose limits on the number of files and total storage capacity, and very large output datasets can become difficult to manage, transfer, and analyse efficiently. These constraints directly affect runtime, scalability, and the feasible evaluation scope of the simulations.

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4.5 Material Transport in Water

The material transport contribution in Deliverable D3.7 outlined the initial strategies for conducting ensemble scenarios, including the variation of particle shapes, sizes, and material properties to assess their influence on simulation outcomes [13]. The work presented in Deliverable D3.8 builds directly upon these concepts, further advancing and implementing the proposed ensemble approaches.

4.5.1 Pilot scope, objectives and decision-making context

The main objective of this pilot is to investigate the physical mechanisms governing particle-laden fluid flows with thermal effects, with a particular focus on conjugate heat transfer in multiphysics systems [4][13]. These flows involve strong coupling between fluid motion, suspended particles, and temperature fields, requiring high-fidelity numerical approaches [13] to accurately capture the underlying transport phenomena. The simulations are carried out using the waLBerla framework, a massively parallel environment for large-scale lattice-based computations. Efficient, architecture-specific computational kernels are generated using lbmpy and pystencils, and integrated into the simulation workflow for production-level runs. An ensemble-based approach is adopted due to the sensitivity of the system to key governing parameters and the complexity of the coupled physics. Systematic parametric studies are required to assess model robustness against benchmark cases and to identify potential limitations. Compared to single simulations, ensemble scenarios provide a more reliable basis for evaluating variability and improving model predictability. The outcomes of this pilot are relevant for understanding particle-laden flows in natural and environmental systems, such as sediment transport in rivers and estuaries, turbidity currents in oceans and lakes, groundwater flows in heated aquifers, and permafrost thawing processes. These applications benefit from improved predictive capabilities, where robustness and sensitivity to varying conditions are of critical importance. At the current stage, the main input parameters include the particle Reynolds number, Prandtl number, and particle volume fraction [4]. The corresponding outputs of interest include flow behaviour, temperature distribution, and particle–fluid interaction characteristics, which together provide insight into the coupled transport processes.

4.5.2 Ensemble setup, varied inputs and methods

The pilot employs a parameter-sweep ensemble approach, where multiple simulation runs are systematically generated by varying key physical and dimensionless parameters. Ensemble members are created using a consistent numerical framework, with each run corresponding to a unique combination of input parameters. This setup enables a structured exploration of the governing physics and supports both model validation and data-driven analysis.

Two different ensemble configurations are considered. The first focuses on high-fidelity simulations of a laminar Couette flow [4] to investigate heat flux budgets in thermal

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particle-laden systems. In particular, the analysis targets the relative contributions of convective and conductive components of phase-specific heat fluxes [4] under varying conditions. In this setup, particles are mobile and the fluid is not thermally stratified. The second configuration is designed to generate large-scale datasets for surrogate modelling [9] and AI-based prediction. This setup considers a simplified scenario with fixed particles and a thermally stratified fluid.

Across the ensemble members, key parameters are systematically varied which include dimensionless parameters effecting the flow regime, thermal properties, geometric characteristics, and boundary conditions. For the Couette flow studies, the particle Reynolds number is varied in the range from 1 to 16, particle volume fraction between 0.1, 0.2 and 0.3, and Prandtl number between 1 and 2 [4], with further higher prandtl number ranges planned in later stages of the project. For the surrogate data generation, parameters such as particle diameter, Rayleigh number, thermal boundary conditions, and particle-to-fluid conductivity ratio [9][13] are varied to span a broad range of physical scenarios.

The exploration space for the two different ensemble simulation runs covers both flow-driven and thermally driven regimes. These setup supports multiple perspectives outlined in D3.8, including input-space exploration, sensitivity-oriented analysis, and AI-oriented ensemble generation for surrogate model development.

4.5.3 Tools, Frameworks, workflow and execution environment

The ensemble simulations are performed using the waLBerla framework, a massively parallel lattice Boltzmann based environment designed for high-performance computing. To ensure computational efficiency and portability across architectures, optimized C++ kernels are generated using lbmpy and pystencils. These tools enable automated generation of hardware-specific kernels, which are directly integrated into the simulation workflow.

The execution workflow is designed to support large-scale parametric studies through automated job generation. Input parameters are first defined in a master bash script which then generates multiple batch job scripts. These scripts can either be executed individually or submitted collectively for multi-job execution. The total number of simulation cases is determined by the combinations of parameters specified for the ensemble. Simulations are executed on HPC systems using Slurm for job scheduling and resource allocation.

For the Couette flow studies, multiple simulations are run in parallel using multi-batch submission to efficiently utilize available computational resources. In contrast, for the surrogate data generation workflow, simulations are executed sequentially one after another as all of them were executed on GPUs, while still following the same automated scripting approach for case generation and execution.

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Post-processing and data management are tailored to the specific ensemble configurations. For the Couette flow studies, simulation outputs are collected into dedicated directories using additional job scripts, enabling structured data organization and streamlined analysis through Python-based post-processing tools.

For the surrogate data generation workflow, where significantly larger data volumes are produced (typically ranging from 100 GB to 1 TB per simulation in VTI format), an additional data reduction step is applied. In this case, simulation outputs are converted to HDF5 format immediately after each run, substantially reducing storage requirements and enabling efficient handling of large datasets for downstream processing and surrogate model development.

4.5.4 Results and Findings

The ensemble scenarios resulted in a substantial number of high-fidelity simulations across both physics-based and data-generation workflows. For the Couette flow ensemble [4], a total of 96 simulations were executed, each utilizing 1024 CPU cores, corresponding to an overall usage of 98,304 CPU cores. This meets and exceeds the targeted KPI requirement of 80,000 CPU cores.

Out of these runs, 76 simulations successfully reached convergence, while 20 simulations did not complete within the maximum allowed wall-clock time of 24 hours. The incomplete runs are primarily attributed to the strict convergence criteria imposed, which required longer runtimes than permitted within the allocated execution window. In addition, a subset of simulations (10 runs each) was executed on different architectures, including the Leonardo Booster partition and the Deucalion ARM partition, to support deployment activities and assess application performance across heterogeneous HPC environments. The figures below demonstrate a couple of results of the ensemble runs of the Couette flow problem where the heat flux budgets are estimated for different parameters. For a wide range of particle Reynolds number, Prandtl number and volume fraction, the heat flux distributions are significantly altered [4][13] as demonstrated in figures. This further supports the argument that ensemble simulation runs are very important for the considered problem at hand.

For the surrogate data generation workflow, more than 100 simulations were completed on GPU-based systems, with each run utilizing 8 NVIDIA A100 GPUs. These simulations produced large-scale datasets intended for training and validating surrogate and AI-based models for thermal particle-laden flows.

A key observation from the ensemble study is the significant variation in performance across different hardware architectures. In particular, the ARM-based partition on Deucalion was found to be less suitable for large-scale production runs for the current application, as it exhibited considerably longer simulation times compared to other platforms. In contrast, systems such as Leonardo demonstrated better performance and scalability for the workloads considered.

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The simulations were conducted across multiple HPC environments, including EuroHPC systems and local university clusters at FAU, ensuring both robustness of execution and portability of the developed workflows. Overall, the ensemble campaign successfully generated a diverse set of simulation outputs and datasets, enabling both detailed physical analysis and the development of data-driven modelling approaches. Representative snapshots of the particle-laden Couette flow for the three Reynolds-number configurations are shown in [Figure 7](#), [Figure 8](#) and [Figure 9](#), respectively.

Figure 7: Re = 9, vol-fraction = 0.3, Pr=2 [4]

Figure 8: Re =1 vol-fraction=0.3,Pr=2

Figure 9: Re =16 vol-fraction=0.3,Pr=2

4.5.5 Summary, limitations and next steps

The ensemble campaign conducted in this pilot addresses two complementary objectives: (i) assessing the robustness and stability of the numerical model across a

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defined parameter space, and (ii) generating large-scale datasets for the development of surrogate AI models. These objectives were realized through two distinct configurations, namely a laminar Couette flow setup for model validation and robustness analysis [4], and a thermally stratified particle-laden system with fixed particles for data generation [9]. Together, these ensemble scenarios contribute to both physics-based understanding and data-driven modelling within the project.

At the current stage, the ensemble setup can be considered functionally mature, with established workflows for large-scale execution, data handling, and deployment across multiple HPC environments. The main value achieved lies in the successful generation of a diverse set of simulation results, enabling both systematic exploration of parameter sensitivities and the creation of high-quality datasets for AI-based surrogate modelling. Despite these achievements, several limitations remain. The current studies are primarily restricted to low Prandtl number regimes, and extending the analysis to higher Prandtl numbers represents an important next step [4][13] for improving model applicability. In addition, while surrogate data generation is computationally efficient, the large volume of generated data introduces significant storage and data management challenges, requiring careful implementation of data reduction strategies. Furthermore, performance limitations were observed on ARM-based HPC partitions, where significantly longer runtimes were required compared to other architectures, impacting their suitability for large-scale production runs.

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5 Conclusions

The deliverable, D3.8, presents the ensemble scenario developments within the HiDALGO2 project, covering methodological foundations, enabling technologies, and pilot-specific implementations across five application domains. The work was structured around the ensemble lifecycle identified across the contributing pilots — defining sources of variation, generating ensemble members, executing them on high-performance computing infrastructure, analysing the outputs statistically, and using the results for uncertainty quantification and decision support. All five pilots — Urban Air Project, Urban Building, Renewable Energy Sources, Wildfires, and Material Transport in Water — have each contributed completed ensemble implementations tailored to their respective domains, demonstrating that ensemble-based simulation is operational across the HiDALGO2 pilot portfolio with working pipelines from parameter definition through HPC execution to statistical output.

The Urban Air Project pilot has executed a full-factorial ensemble of 48 steady-state NO₂ dispersion simulations over a 10.6 million cell mesh of the Győr city geometry, systematically varying 16 wind directions and 3 wind speeds. Singular Value Decomposition of the resulting concentration fields identifies the dominant spatial dispersion patterns and the effective degrees of freedom, providing a basis for reduced-order modelling and scenario-based urban air-quality assessment. The Urban Building pilot has implemented a reproducible ensemble framework within the KUB simulation engine, supporting Monte Carlo and Latin Hypercube sampling, MPI-based parallel execution, online statistical reduction via the Welford/Chan algorithm, and a scenario catalogue with auditable lock-file provenance — providing city planners and energy analysts with robust building rankings, exceedance probabilities, and quantile-based uncertainty indicators for energy demand and thermal comfort assessment. The Renewable Energy Sources pilot has conducted sensitivity analyses with up to 625 ensemble members on up to 70,000 CPUs, demonstrating through Polynomial Chaos Expansion and Sobol indices that wind direction is the dominant uncertainty driver for local wind-speed predictions, while temperature and pressure perturbations have negligible influence. The Wildfires pilot has integrated the 50-member ECMWF MARS meteorological ensemble with multiple ignition-point scenarios and planetary boundary layer parameterisation experiments, producing the first comprehensive probabilistic assessment of wildfire behaviour under combined meteorological, ignition, and model-physics uncertainties, and showing that ensemble agreement decreases over simulation time. The Material Transport in Water pilot has executed 96 Couette flow simulations and over 100 surrogate-generation runs across CPU and GPU architectures, demonstrating that heat flux budgets are significantly altered across the studied parameter ranges and producing large-scale datasets suitable for AI-based surrogate model development.

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Looking across the five pilots, several cross-cutting insights emerge. The pilots employ fundamentally different ensemble generation strategies — full-factorial parametric sweeps, statistical sampling, physics-informed perturbation, operational ensemble reuse, and systematic parameter sweeps — yet they all follow the same define–generate–execute–analyse–use lifecycle. This methodological diversity is a strength rather than a limitation, demonstrating that the ensemble framework is an adaptable methodology that each pilot has shaped to its domain. All five pilots have demonstrated that ensemble-based uncertainty quantification is computationally feasible on EuroHPC and national HPC systems, from the Urban Building pilot's online statistical reduction within a single MPI allocation to the Renewable Energy pilot's campaigns spanning 70,000 CPUs. Where sensitivity analysis was performed, the results consistently narrow the focus to actionable priorities: wind direction matters more than temperature or pressure for energy forecasting, certain ignition points produce anomalous fire propagation, specific parameter regimes in particle-laden flows fail to converge within allocated wall-clock time, and SVD analysis of urban air-quality ensembles reveals the effective dimensionality of pollutant dispersion under varying wind conditions.

The ensemble scenarios and outputs described in this deliverable provide the foundation for several downstream activities in Work Package 4. The sensitivity analyses from the Renewable Energy Sources pilot will be extended in Deliverable D4.10 (Uncertainty Quantification). The surrogate training datasets from the Material Transport pilot feed directly into D4.5 (Advances in HPDA and AI for Global Challenges). The probabilistic fire-impact maps from the Wildfires pilot and the building-stock uncertainty indicators from the Urban Building pilot contribute to the decision-support and AI-analysis objectives of D4.3, D4.4, and D4.5. The SVD-based reduced-order modelling foundations from the Urban Air Project pilot support future efficient reconstruction of dispersion scenarios for urban planning applications. The ensemble lifecycle, tools, and pilot-specific implementations documented in this deliverable establish a solid technical and methodological basis for these continuing activities and for the remaining project period.

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